

Hello, I am <<investigator name>>, <<role>> at the <<Anonymous>>.

<<if more investigators>>

I am accompanied by my supervisor, <<name>>, <<role>> at the <<Anonymous>>.

<<end>>

Thank you very much for taking part in this study.

I hope you have gone through the information sheet.

<<if not>>

please take some time to go through it.

<<end>>

Before starting off, I would like you {all} to know that this {interview/focus group} is being audio recorded.

And after transcribing is done, this audio recording will be deleted.

Also please know that there are no right or wrong answers, we are just looking for your perspective.

Hope you {all} are comfortable with everything and would like to start with the interview?

Topic 1: Participant demographics- (For Separation of Higher Management with Developers)

- job role.
 - Q: what do you do in COMPANY? And when did you join?
- day to day activities.
 - Q: what would your typical day-to-day activities be like?

Topic 2: Challenges in day-day activities- (RQ 4)

Q: In your day-to-day activities, do you face any challenges? They don't have to be technical.

- <<if no challenges>>
 - Prompt: these challenges could be anything, from coding to time management, work pressures.
- <<if challenges related to sustainability>>
 - Prompt: These challenges don't necessarily be due to sustainability. They could be personal to your work as well.
- Resolve steps, if any.

Topic 3: Awareness on sustainability concepts- (RQ 1, RQ 2)

Q: are you aware of any sustainability concepts? Like they don't have to be from software engineering. They could be like in general as well.

- Gained this knowledge from? Studies? Self-study? UN SDGS? Any frameworks?
- <<If yes for studies>>
 - which course and university.
 - part of curriculum or instructor's interest?

Topic 4: Sustainability meaning- (RQ 1, RQ 2)

- In general
 - Q: From your perspective, what does sustainability in general mean for you?
- Sustainable software engineering
 - Q: Now if we think about software engineering, would you think your perspective about sustainability in general be the same? or do you perceive it to be any different?

Topic 5: Awareness on organisation's sustainability efforts- (RQ 1, RQ 2, RQ 3)

- View of participants towards these efforts?
 - Q: are you aware of any initiatives that COMPANY does for sustainability?
 - Q: are there any initiatives in the context of software engineering?

Topic 6: Current sustainable practices in participant's role- (RQ 1, RQ 2, RQ 3)

- Mandated or voluntary.
 - Q: The practices you mentioned, are these mandated by the organisation? Or are these your personal interest?
- Challenges.
 - Q: The practices you mentioned, do you face any challenges to follow them?

Topic 7: Organisation's priority towards sustainable SE- (RQ 3)

Q: do you think that the organization has any priority over sustainability in software engineering?

- Should be prioritized, yes, or no? why?

Topic 8: Benefits from sustainable SE- (RQ 3)

- SE teams.
 - Q: let us assume if your organization has prioritized sustainability within software engineering teams. What benefits do you think that your team or any other team within this area could benefit from?
- Organisational.

- Q: What about your organisation? Can you think of any benefits your organisation could gain?

<<if not practicing currently>>

Topic 9: Challenges from sustainable SE- (RQ 4)

- SE teams.
 - Q: let us assume if your organization has prioritized sustainability within software engineering teams. What challenges do you think that your team or any other team within this area could face when incorporating these practices?
- Organisational.
 - Q: What about your organisation?

<<end>>

Topic 10: Stakeholders for sustainable SE- (RQ 5)

Q: Who do you think are the stakeholders for incorporating sustainability into software engineering teams?

Topic 11: Dedicated team for sustainable SE practices- (RQ 5)

Q: Do you think that there is a requirement for having a dedicated sustainability team?

That is all for this {{interview/focus group}}.

Thank you very much for your time and your answers.

Do you have any questions to ask?

Once again thank you very much for taking part in this study.

Have a good day!